

Creating a Supportive Learning Environment: Grade Two Teachers Point of View

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Abstract. This study investigated and delved into the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights gained from Grade Two teachers regarding the establishment of a supportive learning environment. The research adopted a qualitative phenomenological approach involving ten (10) Grade Two teachers from the Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The exploration of grade two teachers' experiences in creating a supportive learning environment revealed vital observations, including challenges in classroom management, teacher-student relationships, promoting student engagement, and teacher burnout. In examining the coping mechanisms employed by Grade Two teachers to address challenges in creating a supportive learning environment, the study identified effective classroom management, building positive teacher-student relationships, encouraging active engagement, and prioritizing professional development as significant strategies. Finally, the educational management insights derived from the experiences of high school teachers included creating a safe and inclusive space, recognizing the importance of positive relationships, adopting a student-centered approach, and emphasizing reflection and continuous improvement. These themes serve as valuable input for developing and implementing teacher training programs to equip educators with diverse strategies and techniques essential for creating and maintaining a supportive learning environment. To make this study genuinely valuable, publishing it in a journal was essential.

KEY WORDS

1. Learning Environment 2. Grade Two Teachers 3. Davao City

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1. Introduction

Learning is an emotional process—we feel excitement when learning a new skill, embarrassment about mistakes, and fear of being misunderstood. Fostering positive emotions in your classroom will motivate students to learn, while negative emotions such as stress and alienation will inhibit their learning. Creating a positive and trusting classroom environment is important so teachers can provide their students with the safety and support they need for academic, personal, and professional development. On a global scale, as the New Zealand Ministry of Education, (2018) published, the primary objective for every classroom teacher is to examine specific ways, strategies, or processes to keep learners actively engaged in a continuous learning process to create a conducive learning environment. Every student in this environment feels valued, included, and empowered to complete his or her learning task.

A pleasant learning environment necessitates far more than a classroom with encouraging posters on the walls. It entails fully understanding and meeting the needs of learners and colleagues in a variety of ways. Specific classroom rules, for example, will help set a foundation for a healthy learning environment in which students understand what is expected of them. With that structure in place, learners will feel safer, you will be able to comprehend their needs completely, and you will foster positive well-being. (Prodigy Education, 2022). Undoubtedly, the quality of students' academic performance and achievements is closely linked to the characteristics of the learning environment and the availability of beneficial resources. The educational development process encompasses physical, social, cultural, and psychological aspects, underscoring the importance of a suitable and sufficient environment for effective and successful learning. Moreover, Ezike (2018) examined the correlation between classroom environment, students' academic interest, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Chemistry students in selected Public Secondary Schools in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings revealed meaningful associations between classroom environment and academic achievement, and the combined influence of classroom environment and academic interest also displayed a significant impact. The study, conducted in Bhutan, found that lecturers' competencies—including effective lesson delivery, appropriate instructional methods, unbiased assessment practices, maintaining positive interpersonal relationships, a positive approach, and good classroom behavioral management—can significantly enhance classroom wellbeing and increase students' satisfaction with higher education experiences. This, in turn, supports a better learning environment at higher education institutions. Additionally, the research highlighted that classroom well-being substantially impacts student learning. Key factors contributing to classroom well-being included lecturer competence, interpersonal relationships, behavior management, and the physical environment. Students reported benefiting from a positive learning environment, access to suitable teaching and learning materials, and technologically equipped classrooms when classroom well-being was prioritized (Seden et al., 2020). The study in the Philippines found a significant relationship between the classroom environment and student's academic achievement in a male boarding secondary high school in Cavite. A well-equipped classroom with adequate physical facilities positively influenced students' academic performance. The research concluded that the grade 8 students' level of academic achievement was Satisfactory. It emphasized that when students feel comfortable in their classroom environment, they are more focused on the lessons, allowing them to absorb more information from their teachers and thus gain more academic knowledge (Siega et al., 2020). A supportive learning environment refers to any learning environment - physical or social - that encourages harmonious and equitable interactions among learners, wherein the teacher facilitates the delivery of learning and instruction tasks by emphasizing each learner's potential in a distraction-free classroom (Philippine et al. for Teachers, 2017). This environment for learning is more than merely the physical design of the classroom learning space; it also includes social and interpersonal elements so that learners experience a sense of familial closeness and fellowship to accomplish their particular educational objectives. According to (PPST, 2017), To uphold a supportive learning atmosphere, an accomplished educator must establish appropriate classroom routines that prepare and motivate learners to engage in the learning process actively. In addition to typical pre-instruction preparations, such as organizing chairs, tidying desks, and maintaining cleanliness, the teacher should create specific

routines to foster active participation, cooperation, and collaboration among students during the lesson. Creating productive learning environments is vital for students' academic, emotional, and social achievements in school. Such conducive learning environments do not occur spontaneously or by luck; rather, they are intentionally fostered through deliberate practices like engaging with students positively and displaying constructive behaviors. Researchers have demonstrated the positive effects of having an encouraging learning environment. A supportive learning environment allows students to learn in a safe atmosphere where differences are respected. The absence of judgment allows children to freely express their thoughts and ask questions, resulting in greater participation and knowledge. As a result, learning performance increases as students become more committed in their studies and strive for excellence. According to a study, academic achievement, effective risk-management initiatives, and healthy growth of young people have all been linked

to high-quality learning environments defined by a positive school culture and climate. (AES Impact, 2022) Teachers at Andap Elementary School, located in the Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, are actively seeking strategies to establish a research-based supportive learning environment. They are cognizant that the physical and social elements of a supportive learning environment play significant roles in the overall development of learners. Both aspects require attention to genuinely meet learners' needs and foster a supportive atmosphere where everyone feels safe and respected. The physical aspect, which includes classroom structure and condition, should be conducive to fulfilling the learners' basic needs, allowing them to nurture the social aspect. Building healthy relationships with peers and teachers is essential for their social growth. When both components work together harmoniously, they create a truly supportive learning environment for the students.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological research explored the viewpoints of Grade two teachers in public schools regarding establishing a supportive learning environment. The study also examined their coping strategies and the valuable insights gained from the participants' experiences. It is essential to conduct this research study to find out how the teachers will help their learners support their desire to learn. Likewise, when students feel the support of their teachers, both learner performance and completion rates will increase. Good, timely learner support is the difference between success and failure for such students.

1.2. Research Questions—The research aims to gather opinions and firsthand accounts of grade two school teachers working in public schools about creating a supportive learning environment. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the perspectives of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment?
- (2) How do elementary teachers cope with the challenges of creating a supportive learning environment?
- (3) What are the educational insights learned from the experiences of the informants?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following are the terms used to make the study more comprehensive Supportive Learning Environment - refers to any learning environment - physical or social - that encourages harmonious and equi-

table interactions among learners, wherein the teacher facilitates the delivery of learning and instruction Obstacles to Creating a Supportive Learning Environment – refer to the challenges and experiences of teachers.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries.

Department of Education Officials. The DepEd officials ought to be more open, accepting, and understanding when it comes to creating a supportive learning environment and the challenges that follow, especially in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. It might be possible to formulate specific policies to support teachers in creating a conducive learning environment and maximizing their capacity to deliver high-quality instruction. The teachers. The discoveries from this research will offer valuable insights to teachers, as it reveals the par-

1.5. Theoretical Lens—Gregory, Cornell, and Fan's (2011) school climate theory guided this study, which aims to explain how students perceive and experience their school environment. This theory suggests that the school learning environment is shaped by multiple factors, such as academic activities, safety, community, and institutional environment, influencing students' cognitive, behavioral, and psychological development. Consequently, the school climate, regardless of its origin, directly and indirectly impacts students' outcomes, including their academic performance. Classroom Climate refers to warmth and support within a learning context. Fearless teachers improve teaching and learning by reflecting on their practices and cultivating a supportive, inclusive, accessible, and equitable climate. Subsequent researchers expanded on the School Climate Theory by identifying elements that foster positive student development. For instance, Wang and Degol (2015) drew from studies on parenting styles and child development to propose that an authoritative school climate promotes positive student growth. They

participants' perspectives on the difficulties faced while establishing a supportive learning environment and the strategies they have employed to overcome these challenges. The learners. This research will provide the reader with a complete sense of how teachers manage and overcome difficulties in creating a supportive learning environment. This study would also explore grade two teachers' significant challenges and experiences in creating a supportive learning environment. Future researchers. Future researchers should consider some other components of the grade two teachers' experiences that were not covered in this study. To get a better comparison of the phenomenon being studied, additional areas pertaining to this study may be conducted in other grade levels and districts.

defined a positive school climate as one that fosters a democratic atmosphere, allowing students to express themselves freely. To identify an authoritative school climate, Wang and Degol focused on two leading indicators: democratic disciplinary structures and warm student support. In the current study, the term "school climate" is used interchangeably with "school learning environment" to encompass the various elements of the school setting that directly and indirectly influence student learning. Therefore, a conducive student learning environment will positively impact academic performance, while an unfavorable one may have the opposite effect. Shown in Figure 1 is the interconnection between the two research questions, the Experiences of Grade two teachers in Creating a Supportive Learning Environment, and the Coping mechanism for the challenges encountered by Grade two teachers in Creating a Supportive Learning Environment that would result in the common denominator which is Insights Learned from the experiences of secondary school teachers from transition to full in-person classes.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and the ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) was optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—Patton (2002) describes phenomenology as an exploration aimed at understanding the structure and essence of individuals' experiences with a specific phenomenon. This research aligns with that definition, seeking to grasp the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment. However, Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to anticipate a more thorough and detailed investigation than the initial description might indicate. He likened the information provided to just the tip of an iceberg, suggesting that much greater depth and complexity lie beneath the surface. The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stange (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigm a "basic set of belief that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment are discussed by the participants and tries to look into their coping mechanisms in addressing the challenges and educational insights learned. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. It was made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making

personal bias as the study progresses. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln as cited by Creswell (2012) state that on the epistemological assumption, I lessen the distance between myself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. This study intended to gather information from the participants or grade two teachers from Laak North District as to how they created a supportive learning environment. It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used in preparing for school

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology differs from method in that it embodies a creative and adaptive approach to exploring questions and topics, whereas method pertains to the specific knowledge and procedures involved (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment at Laak North District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher’s drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline

emergencies. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that I openly discuss the values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtain from the participants was ensured. I understand the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserved the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpret the answers in the light of the participants’ interpretation. Rhetoric. It means that reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it means that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, I used the first person in elucidation of the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment.

cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world

is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and

the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), I projected that the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment were explored, and insights learned were the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, I was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with the roots in philosophy, psychology and education, phenomenology attempt to extract the purest, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, I used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking of notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects’ perspective. Creswell, (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one

or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews also useful to follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), I transcribed and typed the data into a computer file, in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant’s experiences and pursuing in-depth information around a topic. I collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that was extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. I incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed

out. I required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects that were selected into the study were individuals who have actually experienced the phenomenon. I needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. I also needed to decide as to how and when his or her personal observations be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches was based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasize the importance of personal

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes were large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. They are obtaining most or all of the perceptions that lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There were no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. I needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. I needed to adhere to promoting the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. As a researcher, I focused on the social value of the experiences of disaster risk

perspective and interpretation. As such they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study to explore and assess the experiences and feelings of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in the provision for school's emergency, I employed the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may be best determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). Ten (10) teachers from Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, participated in this study. They were chosen based on the following criteria: they must have been in the service for at least five years, be elementary school grade two teachers, and be experienced in creating a supportive learning environment. I utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). This method is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996).

reduction management coordinators. Specifically, I conducted this research among elementary disaster risk reduction management coordinators. I also aimed to provide insights for higher authorities to develop more programs and resolutions that would benefit these coordinators. The social issue that sparked my interest revolves around the challenges grade two teachers face in creating a supportive learning environment. Informed Consent. In this study, I prioritized following the Treaty Principle of

Participation, as referenced by McLeod (2009). I took care to invite participants in a manner that emphasized their autonomy, ensuring that their involvement was wholly voluntary. I provided all the necessary information to support their understanding, allowing them to make informed choices about their participation in the research. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. I could answer the research instrument since I am a professional teacher in a public elementary school. Thus, I assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case of any clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. I recruited the respondents without using coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Furthermore, I ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. As a researcher, I observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their natural sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so that there would be no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. During the data-gathering process, I informed the respondents of my role and described their roles. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any communication related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. As a researcher, I accessed the study results along with the respondents and heads of the participating schools, as the information was made available on CDs or other storage devices that I could request. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they had the right to withdraw their information at

any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could request and be allowed to verify their transcripts after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. I reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. I assure you that I possess the needed qualifications to conduct the study. I have completed my academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain my master's degree, and am qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. I strived to complete this study successfully within the specified time, and I was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped me enhance the paper

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—I was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and leveraging knowledge to benefit educational institutions. During my study, I embraced the following roles: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I conducted the interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. To avoid the intrusion of bias, I interpreted the ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies rather than on my own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings. Expert in qualitative methods. I implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, I assessed myself and sought help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design,

by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, I ensured that I had enough funds to continue and finish this research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. I respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, I expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication. I respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her own way. I also used quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, I ensured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or purposefully put forward conclusions that were not accurate.

making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing environmental triangulation and thematic content analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. I ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis began. I kept records and properly secured them as they contained sensitive information that was relevant to the research. However, it was my primary responsibility to safeguard the collected data for the participants. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began.

Data Analyst. I ensured that the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective was gathered by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. I also ensured that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. I organized and presented data. I presented the problem and the related literature

and studies that support it. I also presented the study's findings by research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, I gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. *Data Collection*—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. I submitted the revised manuscript of my proposal defense to the ethics committee, fulfilling the requirement for an ethics certificate. I made these revisions carefully, incorporating the thoughtful comments and suggestions provided by the committee to ensure that my proposal meets the necessary ethical standards. I was securing endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. I asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent to ask permission to conduct the study. I asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. I sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the study's objectives and the identification of the participants. I waited for the SDS's response before I conducted it. I asked the Public School District Supervisor for permission. After securing the SDS's approval, I sent letters to the supervisor explaining the study to be conducted in their cluster/district. I asked permission from the school heads. After securing the PSDS's approval, I sent letters to the principals

of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. I asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would go through as participants. Conducting the interview. I conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. I took the participants' profiles, jotted down notes, and recorded conversations using a sound recorder for easy transcription. I listened carefully and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. I transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, I translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data was compared and contrasted. I conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gath-

ered data. I analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using

Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. I immersed myself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element in many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. I coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. I ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. I reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme

was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors were changed to see if the findings were the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, validity was established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research would utilize Colaizzi's method of 1978. The researchers use a rigorous and robust qualitative method to find, understand, describe, and depict the experiences of persons as they experience them, as well as reveal emergent themes and their interwoven relationships. This method aims to uncover the genuine experience of the phenomenon under investigation. Colaizzi's method consists of seven steps. First, informants' descriptions

of the experiences are read to acquire a sense of the whole. After that, significant statements are extracted, Then meanings are formulated from the significant statements. Afterward, formulated meanings are organized into themes. Themes are then integrated into an exhaustive description. Next, the essential structure of the phenomenon is formulated. Finally, for validation, the informants will evaluate the analysis result and if it means the same as their original experiences. (H. Turunen et al. 1994). Fig-

ure 2 shows the steps in the study's analytical framework, which involves familiarization, cod-

ing, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the research study's result and finding would depend on how the researcher conducts it. The trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability was how the qualitative researcher demonstrated that the research study's findings applied to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizers to teach reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students' perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context

and can able to address that core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that "how a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter delves into the results derived from the analysis of interview data. It emphasizes the recognized themes and provides detailed discussions per the study's goals. The main emphasis is on presenting the background and characteristics of the participants, each of whom has been assigned pseudonyms to protect their confidentiality.

3.1. Experiences Of Grade Two Teachers In Creating A Supportive Learning Environment—Establishing a nurturing learning atmosphere is a fundamental duty of educators. Teachers hold a crucial position in shaping students' academic path and overall growth. A conducive learning environment cultivates a positive setting wherein students sense their significance, receive encouragement, and are motivated to realize their maximum potential. The experiences of teachers in constructing such a supportive atmosphere are pivotal in influencing the aca-

3.1.1. Challenges in classroom management—Navigating the complexities of classroom management involves educators adopting strategies to establish and sustain an environment conducive to effective teaching. This encompasses decisions regarding the structure, organization, and class interactions that guide students' behavior and fulfill their expectations (Center for Teaching and Learning, 2023). Classroom management holds a crucial role in the educational process, facilitating the successful implementation of the curriculum and creating an environment conducive to learning. Through the application of effective management strategies, teachers can leave a positive impact on students, setting class expectations and fostering an optimal learning atmosphere (Isuku, E. J. 2018). However, classroom management is not without its challenges for teachers. The disruptive behaviors exhibited by students can be disheartening, to the extent that some educators may contemplate leaving the profession in search of alternative employment (Isuko, 2018). A study by Samaddar, Mukherjee, and Sikder

demical and personal progress of their students. Despite facing obstacles, dedicated educators remain devoted to creating an inclusive, empowering, and encouraging ambiance within their classrooms. Through the cultivation of positive connections, implementation of effective teaching methods, and recognition of the distinct needs of each student, teachers significantly contribute to fostering the development, confidence, and passion for learning in students. Ultimately, this preparation equips students for success in their educational journey and beyond.

(2023) pinpointed several significant challenges in this realm. Firstly, the teacher-student ratio in many developing countries is imbalanced, with a substantial number of students for each teacher, sometimes reaching ratios like 45:1. Managing such a large group becomes exceedingly difficult. Secondly, inattentive learners pose an issue in the classroom. Many students lack focus and often fail to complete assignments, presenting a challenge for teachers to keep them engaged. Thirdly, the complexities of child psychology contribute to classroom management challenges, as some students may be psychologically disturbed, unmotivated, and inattentive, creating a disruptive and noisy classroom environment. Fourth, teachers often face time constraints, with limited time available to cover the curriculum. The rush to complete the curriculum within a short period may hinder proper interaction between students and teachers, leading to a lack of interest in the subject. Fifth, classroom size is a significant problem, especially when the number of students exceeds the capacity of the room. Teachers handling

large classes, sometimes over sixty students, can face difficulties in ensuring proper accommodation and visibility for all students. Overall, these challenges make classroom management a complex and demanding task for educators, requiring innovative solutions to address each issue effectively. The importance of cultivating positive student-teacher relationships emerged as a significant theme in our study, emphasizing its role in creating a supportive learning environment. Participant 5 described this relationship as the "magic ingredient" for a conducive learning atmosphere, highlighting that a genuine connection transcends academic achievements and fosters mutual understanding. This sentiment was echoed by Participant 10, who noted that such relationships enhance student engagement and participation while reducing anxiety about

3.1.2. Positive Student-Teacher Relationship—The responses align with the stated study. Creating a positive student-teacher relationship within the classroom involves establishing trust and mutual respect. This connection is nurtured through efforts to understand students better, providing choices, and encouraging continuous improvement in their learning abilities. By demonstrating respect, appreciation for uniqueness, and politeness, teachers contribute to a safe and inclusive learning environment for all (Coristine, S., Russo, S., Fitzmorris, R., Beninato, P., Rivolta, G. 2022, April 1). In the classroom setting, the benefits of student-teacher relationships are evident. Students who enjoy a positive connection with their teacher develop stronger social-emotional skills and tend to acquire more academic knowledge. This robust relationship fosters confidence in academic pursuits, encouraging students to engage in exploration and risk-taking, ultimately leading to improved classroom performance (Positive teacher-student connections offer cascading effects, 2021). Highlighted is the critical role of student-teacher relationships in the effective-

ness of a classroom, offering both short and long-term benefits. In the short term, these relationships contribute to a thriving classroom environment, bolstering students' self-worth and positively influencing their mental health. Additionally, positive connections can mitigate behavioral issues and promote academic success. Over the long term, a positive student-teacher relationship instills lasting confidence in students, validating the value of their ideas. This enduring confidence positively affects students' social and emotional aspects and their approach to learning from mistakes. By nurturing such positive relationships, students gain enduring confidence and a favorable perspective on their academic journey (Coristine et al., G. 2022, April 1; Buffet, 2019). The study highlighted the critical role of student engagement in fostering a positive classroom environment. Participant 6 likened student engagement to the heartbeat of a classroom, emphasizing its significance in making learning meaningful rather than simply filling time. Participant 4 echoed this sentiment, noting that active participation creates a sense of shared involvement, transforming the classroom

into an inviting space. Participant 10 emphasized the transformative impact of genuine student interest and involvement, emphasizing that it goes beyond academic performance to create a positive social atmosphere where everyone

feels valued. This sentiment was further supported by Participant 1, who noted that student engagement sparks curiosity, ignites creativity, and fosters a sense of community.

3.1.3. Promoting Student Engagement— Researchers in higher education studying college learning define student engagement as the mental state experienced by students during the learning process, representing the convergence of emotions and cognitive processes (Barkley Major, 2020, p. 6). Engaged students surpass passive content absorption; they actively strive to comprehend the material, apply intellectual effort, and grapple with intricate concepts. These learners exhibit a genuine interest in the subject, display motivation and enthusiasm for learning, and take ownership of their educational journey. Expanding on these ideas, Barkley and Major (2020) posit that student engagement results from the interplay of motivation, which propels an individual's behavior, and active learning, the actions students take to develop their skills. It is essential to acknowledge that the blend of motivation and active learning varies for each person, and engagement is not a constant state across time or for a specific individual. Engagement can fluctuate in intensity and may be influenced by the situation; a student may feel enthusiastic about one class while apprehensive about another. Additionally, motivation interacts with other interconnected aspects of learning, such as self-efficacy, an individual's belief in their ability to accomplish a task (Foster, 2023). Furthermore, Foster (2023) emphasizes the need to recognize that engagement can manifest differently for various students or student groups. For example, students from a culture that emphasizes showing respect by refraining from interrupting elders or figures of authority may be hesitant to participate in a full-class discussion. Nonetheless, they might still be highly engaged in listening and contem-

plating the subject matter, possibly preferring participation in small group discussions or writing activities. Moreover, students might choose not to engage if they fear ridicule for providing an incorrect answer or perceive an unsafe environment. According to Sutton, E. (2023), student engagement can be likened to the adhesive that binds all aspects of student learning and development together. High student engagement makes the teaching process more enjoyable, captivating, and fulfilling and yields crucial benefits for students. When students demonstrate strong levels of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement, they are more likely to excel academically, form a deeper connection with their school, and experience enhanced social-emotional well-being. Conversely, low student engagement is associated with adverse outcomes, including delinquency, violence, substance abuse, and school dropout. While these concerning consequences often manifest during adolescence, experiencing poor engagement in elementary and middle school can set students on an unfavorable path. Therefore, fostering and promoting student engagement throughout all grade levels is imperative. The detrimental impact of teacher burnout on the classroom environment emerged as a significant concern in the study. Participants highlighted how burnout drains energy and passion from teaching, resulting in decreased patience, creativity, and support for students (Participant 3). This exhaustion affects the teacher-student bond, which is vital for fostering a positive learning atmosphere (Participant 5). Participant 8 emphasized that burnout may lead to increased teacher absenteeism and a decline in teaching quality, undermining efforts to maintain a positive class-

room environment. Participant 2 underscored the challenge of connecting with students personally when teachers are emotionally drained, further highlighting the negative consequences of burnout on the teacher-student relationship. These insights underscore the importance of addressing teacher burnout as a critical factor in creating and sustaining a positive classroom environment. Implementing strategies to support teacher well-being and prevent burnout is essential for maintaining a supportive and engaging learning environment for students.

3.1.4. Teacher Burnout—In 2019, the World Health Organization (WHO) updated its definition of burnout: Burnout is a syndrome arising from prolonged workplace stress that remains unresolved. It manifests through three dimensions: 1) feelings of exhaustion or depletion of energy; 2) increased mental distance from one's job, leading to negative attitudes or cynicism towards work; and 3) reduced effectiveness and professional efficacy (WHO, 2019). Teachers' well-being and workload can impact their ability to create and sustain a supportive learning environment. Addressing teacher burnout and providing adequate support to educators is essential for promoting a positive learning environment. Teacher stress can harm student performance. According to the first meta-analysis of teacher burnout research, which examined 14 studies involving 5,311 teachers and 50,616 students, there is evidence linking teacher burnout to lower academic achievement and reduced quality of stu-

3.2. Mechanisms for Success in Creating A Supportive Learning Environment—Establishing a nurturing learning atmosphere is a collaborative effort involving educators, students, parents, and the broader educational community. By implementing strategies geared toward success, teachers can cultivate a positive, inclusive, and empowering environment conducive to

dent motivation (Madigan Kim, 2021). Teacher burnout is linked to teachers' sense of self-worth and self-efficacy. According to Zaretsky and Katz (2019), teaching involves emotional labor, as schools can elicit both negative and positive emotions. Managing these emotions requires individual regulation, as they may not always align with personal feelings, leading to two common behaviors: adaptive and non-adaptive regulation. Non-adaptive emotion regulation strategies are associated with higher levels of anxiety and depression, while adaptive strategies have the opposite effect. Burnout can be considered a non-adaptive strategy related to emotional labor. This emotional labor significantly impacts teacher efficacy, efficiency, and how teachers perceive themselves and their colleagues (Zaretsky Katz, 2019). Furthermore, teacher burnout is associated with various negative consequences, including increased vulnerability to mental illnesses and irritability. Madigan and Kim (2020) also propose that teacher burnout can lead to lower job morale and absenteeism, ultimately affecting the teachers' overall quality of life and impacting the students. Figure 3 emerges the themes of the Experiences of Grade Two teachers in Creating a Supportive Learning Environment, which were enumerated as follows: Effective Challenges in classroom management, Positive Student-Teacher Relationships, Prompting Student Engagement, and Teacher Burnout. These experiences of teachers are critical to the learners' learning development.

academic and emotional growth. This supportive learning environment goes beyond boosting student engagement and academic achievements; it molds students into lifelong learners, critical thinkers, and responsible societal contributors. As educators persist in prioritizing these strategies, they not only shape the future of their students but also contribute to creating

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Grade Two Teachers in Creating a Supportive Learning Environment

a more compassionate and supportive global community. Effective classroom management emerged as a cornerstone for fostering a positive learning environment in our study. Participants likened it to a superhero that maintains positive classroom vibes and ensures smooth operations (Participant 7). Beyond averting chaos, Participant 10 emphasized that effective management creates an environment conducive to exploration, learning, and collaboration. Par-

ticipant 8 highlighted the productivity and enjoyment that result from a positive atmosphere with fewer disruptions, contributing to a sense of comfort among students and fostering a team-player mentality. Moreover, Participant 1 emphasized that effective classroom management goes beyond discipline; it establishes clear expectations, fostering trust between students and teachers and serving as the backbone of a positive learning space.

3.2.1. Effective Classroom Management— Classroom management is knowing each student's level, and this means that teachers are able to create a learning environment to encourage positive interaction, engagement, and motivation. This includes a plan for rules and procedures, guiding and reinforcing behavior, motivating, and engaging instruction, and enhancing positive student-teacher relationships (Burden, 2020). Classroom management is a continuous journey, and each classroom may differ in its approach. Nevertheless, all classrooms share a common objective: to achieve student success. To attain this goal, teachers must grasp the essence of classroom management, encompassing aspects such as instruction, environment, rules, relationships, and discipline (Rust, 2022). Rust (2022) identified several processes that contribute to effective classroom management. One essential step in the prevention process involves the physical design of the classroom. Rather than being a single uniform space, a classroom comprises interconnected and diverse micro-environments (Sommer, 2001, p. 175). Considering the multitude of activities occurring in a classroom, educators must carefully contemplate every aspect of the space during the design phase. This includes factors such as noise, seating arrangement, lighting, organization, and, most importantly, the needs of the students. In essence, the classroom layout plays a significant role in classroom management, as it

should create a safe and motivating environment that contributes to academic success. Another crucial aspect of effective classroom management is the establishment of rules and routines. Educators often find setting rules and routines to be a significant challenge in the management process. Both rules and routines serve as expectations aimed at preventing behavior problems and maintaining a sense of order in the classroom. Rules generally encompass overall class expectations, while routines are specific to particular tasks or activities. By implementing rules and routines, teachers create a structured environment that helps prevent disruptive behavior and fosters a conducive learning atmosphere (Rust, 2022). Establishing ground rules and routines in the classroom provides the learning community with well-defined and logical expectations. When these rules and routines are created collaboratively, students feel a sense of accountability. Such guidelines enable students to exercise autonomy and understand the impact of their decisions on their peers. By promoting trust, respect, and a sense of responsibility, rules and routines contribute to overall success in the classroom (Schaefer, 2018). Effective classroom management fosters an environment conducive to learning, where students are actively engaged and well-behaved. In contrast, poor classroom management leads to disruptive and disengaged students who may disregard teacher instructions. Creating a well-managed

classroom requires a deliberate focus on essential pillars. Without a comprehensive understanding of these foundational principles, the risk of ineffective management increases, potentially hampering students' academic progress and overall development. (Spencer, n.d) This study illuminated the significance of fostering positive student-teacher relationships as fundamental to creating a supportive classroom environment. Participants emphasized the importance of getting to know students individually and understanding their interests, strengths, and challenges (Participant 4). Effective communi-

cation, characterized by active listening and constructive feedback, emerged as a key element in cultivating trust and value among students (Participant 7). Consistency, fairness, and respect were highlighted by Participant 2 as essential qualities that contribute to building trust with students, forming the foundation of a positive classroom environment where students feel safe and appreciated. Additionally, Participant 1 underscored the importance of recognizing and accommodating diverse backgrounds and learning styles, promoting inclusivity and demonstrating genuine care for student well-being and success.

3.2.2. Building Positive Teacher-Student Relationships—According to the American Psychological Association, enhancing teacher-student relationships has significant and lasting benefits for students' academic progress. Various studies have demonstrated that positive teacher-student relationships contribute to improved academic performance. For example, New York University researchers found a correlation between teacher-student closeness and advancements in elementary students' reading achievement. From preschool to high school, the strength of the bond between students and their teachers greatly influences their academic achievements. A comprehensive review of multiple studies revealed that higher-quality teacher-student relationships were linked to increased student engagement, resulting in improved academic grades (Kime, P. 2023). According to Nel Noddings, an educational philosopher, it is evident that children are more willing to exert effort and undertake tasks, even challenging ones like adding fractions, for individuals they love and trust. Numerous studies, including one featured in the *Journal of School Health*, have shown that teachers who maintain close relationships with their students report lower rates of school avoidance and increased student motivation to learn.

Positive teacher-student relationships draw students deeper into their studies, as they feel motivated to impress an adult who genuinely cares about their success and academic progress (Kime, 2023). Positive and healthy relationships foster positive student behavior. Apart from serving as a motivational factor for student engagement in learning, research indicates that having a caring teacher encourages prosocial behaviors among students. A study conducted by the University of Cambridge revealed that positive teacher-student relationships can be as effective as anti-bullying programs and similar interventions. Specifically, at ages 10 to 11, a strong teacher-student relationship significantly enhanced the development of prosocial behaviors, such as cooperation and altruism. The researchers observed that students with a more positive relationship with their teacher exhibited 18 percent more prosocial behavior towards their peers and displayed up to 38 percent less aggressive behavior towards them. Throughout the day, students' brains are actively learning new skills and making connections between new and existing information. Simultaneously, their brains are continuously processing their relationship with their teacher. Positive student-teacher relationships are essential for academic success. When students feel supported, they

become more engaged in their learning, leading to improved academic outcomes. Moreover, positive interactions with teachers contribute to reduced behavioral problems among students. Building and maintaining these relationships are crucial, especially during uncertain times such as the coronavirus pandemic (Ms, T. K. 2023). The teacher-student relationship has existed for ages, and globally, educators are expected to foster positive connections with their students. Teachers play a significant role in creating lifelong learners, and this cannot be achieved if there is hostility between them and their students. Vygotsky (1978) emphasized that higher mental functioning is shaped through social interactions with teachers and culturally transmitted knowledge. Other researchers have shown that language dialogue between teachers and students enhances cognitive development. Purposeful and positive interactions with teachers can influence students' thinking skills significantly. Vygotsky (1978) highlighted that teacher-student interactions trigger various de-

velopmental processes. Students who establish positive relationships with their teachers can overcome many challenges in school. Educational institutions should support students in cultivating positive relationships with their teachers. (J, A. S., Eyasu, M. 2017) The consensus among participants in the study underscores the pivotal role of active student engagement in shaping a positive classroom atmosphere. Participant 6 highlighted how engagement transforms students into co-creators of the learning experience, sparking curiosity, and igniting creativity. This sentiment was reinforced by Participant 7, who emphasized that active participation fosters understanding, retention of information, and a sense of community where students feel valued. Participant 10 emphasized the necessity of active engagement in creating a dynamic and responsive classroom environment that caters to diverse learner needs. When students actively participate in discussions and activities, learning becomes a collaborative endeavor, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the learning process.

3.2.3. Encouraging Active Engagement— Promoting active engagement is a key mechanism for success in a supportive learning environment. Teachers can encourage students to participate actively in class discussions, group activities, and hands-on projects. By giving students opportunities to collaborate, share their thoughts, and take ownership of their learning, educators empower them to become active and enthusiastic learners. In a 2018 Gallup study, it was observed that as students progress through their academic journey, their level of engagement, characterized by involvement, enthusiasm, and commitment, tends to decline. The study revealed concerning results: In fifth grade, a significant majority (74 percent) of students reported high levels of engagement with school. However, this percentage drops to half in middle school, and further decreases

to about one-third in high school. Even during and after the pandemic, student engagement remained a prominent concern for parents and educators. Remote learning posed challenges in keeping students engaged, as reported by approximately 45 percent of parents, 77 percent of administrators, and 81 percent of teachers. Moreover, an overwhelming 94 percent of educators considered student engagement to be the most critical metric for assessing student success. Gallup's findings indicated that students who are engaged with school not only achieve higher grades but also harbor a more optimistic outlook towards their future (Parrish, N. 2022). Creating a dynamic and successful learning environment hinge on promoting active engagement in the classroom. When students actively participate in their learning, they become more motivated, develop critical think-

ing abilities, and excel academically. Educators can foster this culture of active engagement by incorporating active learning methods, embracing a student-centered approach, and offering opportunities for choice and reflection. This approach empowers students to become active learners and instills a lifelong passion for seeking knowledge. According to an article by the Center for Teaching and Learning (2023), there are several ways to promote student engagement in the classroom. To enhance student participation, educators should invest time and effort in shaping the learning environment and carefully planning each class session. The manner of interaction, both verbal and non-verbal, also communicates the teacher's attitude towards participation. The ultimate objective is to create an inclusive environment where all students have the chance to actively engage in the course and enhance their learning experience. Active learning is also aligned with other theories of learning: One such theory is the notion that learning should be relevant and situated within a meaningful context. This concept was developed by the philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712–1778) and had a significant impact on educators in the early 20th century, including John Dewey (1859–1952) and Maria Montessori (1870–1952). The core principle behind this theory is that students learn most effectively when they can perceive the practicality of what they are learning and establish connections to the real world.

3.2.4. Professional Development—Across the globe, educational reform is a top priority for policymakers and governments, with the aim of enhancing student outcomes and addressing disparities in achievement. Large-scale international assessments play a significant role in comparing performance globally. Additionally, the importance of teachers in driving reform efforts is universally acknowledged and emphasized as they are considered fundamental to the process of improvement and change (Patfield, S., Gore,

J. Harris, 2023) In the modern era, professional development (PD) plays a crucial role in the growth and advancement of educators. With the ever-changing educational landscape, educators need to embrace multiple perspectives, utilize technology, and seize opportunities to foster student learning and development. The aim of PD is not only to maintain competence but also to ensure sustainability and longevity in the teaching profession. As students continuously evolve with technology and access to information, the fundamental principles of being firm, fair, and consistent in their learning still hold true. Effective PD for teachers in the 21st century involves recognizing these core values and exploring innovative ways to enhance teaching and learning strategies. (Yangambi, M. W. 2021). According to the (Education Policy Institute 2021), the following are impact of professional development on learners. High-quality Continuing Professional Development (CPD) for teachers significantly impacts students' learning outcomes. CPD programs have the potential to narrow the gap between novice and experienced teachers, with the effect on pupil outcomes (effect size 0.09) comparable to having a teacher with ten years' experience instead of a new graduate. Moreover, CPD demonstrates similar attainment effects as those brought about by significant structural reforms in the school system. Evidence suggests that the quality of CPD has a more substantial impact on pupil attainment compared to other interventions schools might consider, such as implementing performance-related pay for teachers or extending the school day. Although there are interventions like one-to-one tutoring with higher impacts on pupil attainment. they often come with much higher costs. Teacher CPD proves to be a cost-effective intervention for enhancing student outcomes, as it produces positive responses from teachers. In contrast, large structural changes to the school system, while effective in improving pupil outcomes,

may result in considerable costs related to staff turnover and dissatisfaction. Teachers' professional development is a critical component of creating a successful and thriving educational ecosystem. By investing in the growth and development of educators, we empower them to inspire and motivate students to reach their full potential. Providing teachers with access to high-quality PD opportunities not only benefits them personally and professionally but also contributes to the overall improvement of education and society as a whole. As education continues to evolve, professional development must remain a priority, ensuring that teachers are well-equipped to meet the ever-changing needs of their students and shape a brighter future for generations to come. burnout to lower academic achievement and reduced quality of student motivation (Madigan and Kim, 2021). Teacher burnout is linked to teachers' sense of self-worth and self-efficacy. According to Zaretsky Katz (2019), teaching involves emotional labor, as schools can elicit both negative and positive emotions. Managing these emotions requires individual regulation, as they may not always align with personal feelings, leading to two common behaviors: adaptive and non-adaptive regulation. Non-adaptive emotion regulation strategies are associated with higher levels of anxiety and depression, while adaptive strategies have the opposite effect. Burnout can be considered a non-adaptive strategy related to emotional labor. This emotional labor significantly impacts teacher efficacy, efficiency,

and how teachers perceive themselves and their colleagues (Zaretsky Katz, 2019). Establishing a supportive learning environment poses a significant challenge for teachers if they experience burnout. This not only impacts the students but can also have broader consequences. Teacher burnout has far-reaching effects on society, impacting students, teachers, and educational institutions. According to Madigan and Kim (2020), teacher burnout is linked to low student motivation and poorer academic achievement. Teachers play a central role in students' learning experiences, so their well-being significantly influences classroom activities and student learning outcomes. Furthermore, teacher burnout is associated with various negative consequences, including increased vulnerability to mental illnesses and irritability. Madigan and Kim (2020) also propose that teacher burnout can lead to lower job morale and absenteeism, ultimately affecting the teachers' overall quality of life and impacting the students. Prioritizing the well-being of teachers ensures they can effectively lead and excel in their educational practice. Figure 4 emerges the themes of the mechanisms for success in creating a supportive learning environment, which was enumerated as follows: Effective Classroom Management, Positive student-teacher relationships, building positive student-teacher relationships, encouraging active engagement, and professional development. Teachers' coping mechanisms are vital to their individual motivation and job engagement.

3.3. Insights Learned From The Experiences Of The Informants—Throughout the interview, numerous insights into educational con-

cepts were obtained by exploring instructors' challenges and experiences in creating a supportive learning environment.

3.3.1. Creating a Safe and Inclusive Space—Learning environments should actively engage learners, foster inclusivity, and create

a sense of belonging for all participants, ensuring equal opportunities for involvement. An intentional and organized approach to inclusivity

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Coping Mechanism in Creating a Supportive Learning Environment

in classrooms accommodates the diverse needs of every learner, acknowledging that individuals progress at different paces and may require varied methods to grasp educational material. As educators, it is our responsibility to ensure that the learning environment is accessible and welcoming to all, embracing inclusivity. Encouraging inclusivity in early childhood settings yields various benefits for children, fostering positive attitudes toward school and self while imparting essential life skills such as empathy and compassion (Building an inclusive environment in early childhood classrooms, 2022). The global adoption of inclusive education aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, emphasizing the integration of all children in schools that cater to varying needs through suitable curricula, teaching methods, and resource allocation (UNESCO, 1994). Inclusive education aims to overcome obstacles hindering attendance, involvement, and success, offering diverse students the chance to engage in meaningful and varied learning interactions (Roldán et al., 2021). Psychologists, rooted in Vygotsky and Bruner's sociocultural

theory, stress the significance of social interactions in children's learning and development. Bruner's concept of "communities of mutual learners" highlights the benefits of peer learning interactions. Group work in schools, as communities of mutual learners, balances individuality and group effectiveness, allowing each student to progress according to their abilities. Interactive and dialogic learning environments foster collective thinking, leading to improved academic achievement, social skills, and cohesion, particularly benefiting vulnerable student groups (Fernández-Villardón et al., 2020; García-Carrión et al., 2020). The core emphasis in an inclusive learning environment lies in discovering the most effective approach for each child and adapting instruction to individual needs. Diverse teaching methods engage every student in challenging activities that promote growth and comprehension of new skills and concepts. Ultimately, an inclusive learning environment benefits all students, fostering tolerance, accepting differences, and encouraging self-improvement (Cchiario, 2020).

3.3.2. Importance of Positive Relationships—Prior studies have indicated that positive teacher-student relationships positively impact student academic achievement, resulting in improved grades and test scores. However, a recent study at the University of Missouri highlights that these positive relationships also contribute to better teaching practices. The research underscores the significance of teachers displaying "soft" skills or prosocial behaviors within the classroom. These behaviors encompass acts of kindness, compassion, and care for others, in addition to the conventional teaching of core academic subjects like reading, writing, and arithmetic (Positive teacher-student relationships lead to better teaching – College of Education Human Development, 2022) Strong and

constructive teacher-student relationships form the cornerstone of effective teaching. When students experience positive connections with their teachers, it enhances their social-emotional development and facilitates better academic learning. They exhibit higher test scores, improved grades, and a reduced likelihood of grade retention or special education referrals. Positive teacher-student relationships create a safe and supportive environment for students to tackle challenging academic tasks. These relationships serve as motivation for students to actively participate and invest effort in their learning journey. Christians, K., Christians, K. (2023). Research has consistently shown the significant impact of positive teacher-student relationships across all age groups, from preschool to high

school. This effect is substantial and resilient, even surpassing the influence of curriculum or instructional methods chosen by teachers. While the effect is prominent for all students, it is particularly profound for those facing risk factors such as abuse, neglect, parental drug use, or other challenges. The study conducted by Li, X., Bergin, C., and Olsen, A. (2022) revealed that positive teacher-student relationships not only benefit students but also contribute to improved teaching. In other words, teachers with positive relationships with their students tend to integrate more advanced teaching practices more frequently in the classroom. Investing time in cultivating relationships with students not only benefits the students themselves but also has a profound impact on teachers. It may instill a sense of security, willingness to take risks, or the opportunity to delve deeper into their instructional methods. Whatever the reason, establishing positive connections and relationships with students significantly enhances

teaching practices. One effective approach to foster positive teacher-student relationships is for teachers to create opportunities that motivate students to be actively engaged in the class. Motivational engagement goes beyond cognitive involvement or active participation in learning; it revolves around students feeling connected and immersed in the classroom environment, genuinely desiring to be part of it. (Li, X., Bergin, C., and Olsen, A. 2022) There are multiple approaches to foster emotional engagement in the classroom, but one highly effective strategy is for teachers to infuse their genuine interests, authenticity, and personality into the learning environment. By integrating their unique character strengths and passions, teachers can cultivate positive teacher-student relationships. These connections, in turn, offer students the encouragement and support to participate in more advanced academic teaching practices, thus further promoting a conducive learning atmosphere.

3.3.3. Student-Centered Approach— Student-centered learning is an educational philosophy that customizes the learning experience to address the distinct needs of each student. This approach may involve elements like blended learning, personalized learning models such as a flipped classroom, station rotation, or competency-based learning, often incorporating technology. However, authentic student-centered learning surpasses these models. Regardless of the strategy employed, it involves a collaborative effort between students and teachers to choose a learning path that best fits the individual learner (Green, C. Harrington, C. 2020). In a genuine student-centered learning environment, learning is competency-based, requiring students to demonstrate mastery of individual concepts before advancing through a unit. This approach, as explained by Erin Figula, director of professional learning at LEAP Inno-

vations, promotes progression based on demonstrated proficiency rather than time spent on a subject (Bouffard, 2019). Competency-based progression accommodates diverse learning methods, allowing students to progress at their own pace while showcasing their knowledge. In a true student-centered learning environment, there is continuous monitoring of individual student needs. Technology is utilized to track students' progress, aiding both teachers and students in assessing and adapting learning pathways. According to Harrington and LeBlanc (2019), assessment methods can vary from formal to informal, summative to formative, and may include observation, anecdotal records, portfolios, rubrics, or projects. Continuous monitoring is essential for tailoring the learning experience to each student's needs. Dr. Sarah Pazur, director of school leadership at FlexTech High Schools, asserts that student-

centered learning closely aligns with real-life experiences and workplace demands, emphasizing goal-setting, proactive steps, effective time management, reflection on progress, and openness to improvement. Dr. Pazur emphasizes the importance of students learning to use available resources and connect prior knowledge to solve present challenges (Green, C. Harrington, C. 2020). The Student-Centered Approach (SCA) redefines the teacher's role from an information provider to a creator of learning environments that foster effective learning. Teachers embracing SCA do not limit themselves to a singular teaching method in their lessons (Darsih, 2018). In practice, the concept of student-centered learning can vary significantly from one school to another, depending on the level of implementation chosen by each district or institution. Some school districts may adopt technology-rich personalized learning approaches, blended learning, or customized learning, shifting the teacher's role to that of a guide or facilitator, deviating from the traditional teacher-led model. Regardless of the degree of implementation, the decision of school districts to embrace a more student-centered learning model is motivated by the recognition that adhering to conventional practices might not be in the best interest of students. These schools acknowledge the need for difficult changes to prioritize the well-being and learning needs of students, understanding that traditional practices may not effectively address challenges such as declining test scores, graduation rates, lack of student engagement, or low achievement (Green, C. Harrington, C. 2020). While various learning methods focus solely on learning without considering the broader context or purpose, student-centered learning caters to students' specific needs and preferences. It is designed to be adaptable, offering a diverse range of exercises and content while promoting collaboration and the practical application of knowledge and skills. Implementing this approach demands significant effort from

both students and teachers, but the outcomes are evident and rewarding (Ranido, O. 2023).

3.3.4. Reflecting and Improving—Reflection plays a vital role in the learning and educational process. According to John Dewey, a renowned educational philosopher, reflective thought involves actively and carefully considering our beliefs and knowledge, analyzing the reasons supporting them, and exploring their potential implications. This definition emphasizes that reflection is an active process, enabling individuals to learn from past experiences, construct new knowledge, and apply it to future encounters. Consequently, reflection aligns closely with the essence of education. Dewey further defines education as the process of reconstructing or reorganizing experiences to enhance their meaning and improve one's ability to navigate future encounters. (Lsanchez, 2023). Dewey's educational philosophies emphasize the importance of continuous learning and growth, making reflective thought a crucial aspect for both students and teachers. In this context, both teachers and students should adopt an inquiry-based approach to their roles. Teachers, striving to enhance their students' education, should engage in constant reflection on their teaching methods and content, assessing the effectiveness of their approach. Learning from this reflection, teachers can use the insights gained to inform and improve their future teaching practices. Reflective teaching involves instructors dedicating time to assess their teaching practice, review curricular decisions, take into account student feedback, and make necessary revisions to enhance student engagement and learning. This process entails gathering information, interpreting data, and planning for future improvements. Reflective teaching includes examining one's fundamental beliefs about teaching and learning and ensuring alignment with actual classroom practices before, during, and after the course is taught (Reflective Teaching, 2021) When engaging in reflective teaching, instructors criti-

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes On The Insights Learned From The Experiences Of The Informants

cally analyze their teaching methods and seek evidence of effective teaching. This analysis can draw on four crucial sources, as outlined by Brookfield (2017): "students' perspectives, colleagues' feedback, personal experiences, and relevant theory and research." Instructors can employ various tools and approaches to learn from these sources and reflect on their teaching, ranging from informal self-assessment to formal classroom observations and from considering student evaluations to exploring educational research. Reflective teaching is an ongoing practice, as each semester's students and their needs may vary, and it promotes practical and student-centered teaching. Hence, it is crucial for teachers to consistently enhance

and broaden their professional knowledge and adapt their practices to cater to the diverse learning needs of their students. Our society's dynamic and ever-evolving knowledge landscape necessitates a teaching force that embraces up-to-date information to equip today's students for the challenges of tomorrow's society. Relying on outdated professional knowledge to prepare students for the future is no longer acceptable (Reflective Practice, 2022). Figure 5 emerges with the themes of insight learned by grade two teachers for supporting the environment. These were enumerated: creating a safe and inclusive environment, the importance of positive relationships, students' approach, and reflecting and improving style.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presented a concise overview of the research, followed by conclusions drawn from the study's findings. It also explored prospective paths for educators with expertise in creating a supportive learning environment. Additionally, the chapter delved into the strategies employed to overcome obstacles and extracted insights about education from the experiences shared by the

informants.

4.1. Findings—The findings of the study, drawn from the insightful responses of participants, shed light on the multifaceted dynamics that shape a positive classroom environment. Participants emphasized the pivotal role of student-teacher relationships in fostering a supportive learning atmosphere, highlighting the importance of trust, communication, and understanding. They underscored how active student engagement was the cornerstone of a vibrant classroom, sparking curiosity, igniting creativity, and promoting collaboration among learners. Moreover, the study revealed the significant impact of teacher burnout on the classroom scene, emphasizing the need for strategies to support educator well-being and prevent exhaustion. The finding revealed the themes of the experiences of grade two teachers in creating a supportive learning environment, which was enumerated as follows: effective challenges in classroom management, positive student-teacher relationships, prompting student engagement, and teacher burnout. These experiences of teachers are critical to the learners' learning development. In addition, the themes of the mechanisms for success in creating a support-

ive learning environment were enumerated as follows: effective classroom management, positive student-teacher relationships, encouraging active engagement, and professional development. Teachers' coping mechanisms are vital to their individual motivation and job engagement. Moreover, the themes of insight learned by grade 2 teachers for supporting the environment. These were enumerated: creating a safe and inclusive environment, the importance of positive relationships, students' approach, and reflecting and improving style. Furthermore, the study highlighted the critical importance of continuous professional development for educators in maintaining a positive classroom environment. Participants emphasized how ongoing learning enables teachers to adapt to evolving educational trends, enhance instructional methods, and effectively address the diverse needs of students. They stressed the collaborative nature of professional development, promoting the sharing of ideas and best practices among educators. Overall, the findings underscored the interconnectedness of various factors in cultivating a positive classroom environment, ultimately enhancing student engagement, learning outcomes, and overall well-being.

4.2. Implications—The outcomes of my analysis unveiled notable findings as follows. Interviews were conducted with ten (10) teachers from various schools in the Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, each bringing diverse backgrounds. The experiences of Grade Two teachers in establishing a supportive learning environment yielded four key themes: Challenges in classroom management, Student-Teacher Relationship, Promoting Student Engagement, and Teacher Burnout. The teachers' strategies for creating a supportive learning

environment also resulted in four themes: Effective Classroom Management, Building Positive Teacher-Student Relationships, Encouraging Active Engagement, and Professional Development. These findings are crucial for understanding teachers' challenges and experiences while striving to establish a supportive learning environment. Moreover, it is recommended that policymakers, educators, and anyone interested in enhancing students' educational experiences take into consideration our suggestions and findings.

4.3. Future Directions—

Implementing targeted professional development programs for teachers to enhance their classroom management skills, foster positive student-teacher relationships, and promote active student engagement was imperative. Workshops, seminars, and ongoing training sessions can be designed to address the specific challenges identified in creating a supportive learning environment. Collaborative efforts involving educational institutions, school districts, and educational authorities can contribute to developing and implementing effective professional development initiatives. To address classroom management challenges, it is recommended that teachers be provided with additional resources and tools to effectively manage diverse classroom settings. Implementing clear and consistent rules, employing positive reinforcement techniques, and utilizing innovative teaching methods can contribute to a more conducive learning atmosphere. Furthermore, establishing mentorship programs or peer support networks can provide teachers with valuable insights and guidance in managing classroom challenges. Fostering open communication and creating a sense of trust and respect is crucial for enhancing student-teacher relationships. Professional development programs should emphasize strategies for building positive connections with students, understanding their needs, and incorporating empathy into teaching practices. Additionally, promoting a collaborative approach between teachers, students, and parents can strengthen the overall support system within the learning environment. Interactive and student-centered teaching methodologies should be incorporated to promote student engagement. Encouraging hands-on activities, group discussions, and technology in the classroom can enhance student interest and participation. Recognizing and incorporating students' diverse learning styles and preferences can contribute to a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. In conclusion, the identified themes of challenges in classroom management, student-teacher relationships, promoting student engagement, and teacher burnout underscore the complex nature of creating a supportive learning environment. The coping mechanisms, including effective classroom management, building positive teacher-student relationships, encouraging active engagement, and prioritizing professional development, provide valuable insights for educators. By implementing the recommended strategies and focusing on targeted professional development, educational stakeholders can contribute to creating supportive learning environments that foster positive student outcomes and teacher well-being. Considering these recommendations is paramount for policymakers, educational institutions, and teachers committed to enhancing the overall educational experience for students. Finally, similar qualitative research across the nation may be used to gain a broader understanding and more insights from diverse participants in this study to deepen the information on teachers' experiences in creating a supportive learning environment.

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